

The New Jersey Population Health Cohort Study: Survey Design

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Abstract

The New Jersey Population Health Cohort Study (NJHealth) is the largest study to date to explore factors that influence health and well-being in the state. Led by the Rutgers Institute for Health, Health Care Policy and Aging Research, the study seeks to improve our understanding of how life events and stress affect health and resilience, and identify health disparities encountered by historically disadvantaged groups, multigenerational families, and immigrant groups. The study was designed to enroll and follow longitudinally up to 10,000 participants from across New Jersey, with an emphasis on historically disadvantaged groups, multi-generational families, and immigrant groups, including: South Asian Indian, Chinese, Dominican, Filipino, Korean, Mexican, Nigerian, Afro-Caribbean and/or refugees/asylees.

In this manuscript, attention is given to the study's multi-stage probability sample design, the use of address-based sampling (ABS) and the model-based oversampling strategies utilized to help to increase the yields and precision of survey estimates of recent immigrant populations in the state and of multigenerational households. To help ensure target survey response rates and sample targets are achieved, the sample design is further segmented into three distinct and representative subsamples, surveyed over three distinct data collection operational periods to help best utilize the available field staff in an efficient and effective manner and permitting fast-track study estimates prior to the conclusion of the survey. The estimation and weighting strategies implemented to correct for disproportional sampling, survey nonresponse and poststratification will also be summarized. In addition, planned study investigations are presented that examine ways in which the stress and resilience experiences of the study participants, including factors related to the COVID-19 pandemic, impact their health and well-being.

Key Words: NJ Health Cohort Study; health disparities; multigenerational families; immigrant groups; model-based oversampling; Address Based Sampling (ABS)

1. Background

The New Jersey Population Health Cohort Study (NJHealth) is the largest study to date to explore factors that influence health and well-being in the state. Led by the Rutgers Institute for Health, Health Care Policy and Aging Research, the study seeks to improve our understanding of how life events and stress affect health and resilience, and identify health disparities encountered by historically disadvantaged groups, multigenerational families, and immigrant groups. The study was designed to enroll and follow longitudinally up to 10,000 participants from across New Jersey, with an emphasis on historically disadvantaged groups, multi-generational families, and immigrant groups, including: South Asian Indian, Chinese, Dominican, Filipino, Korean, Mexican, Nigerian, Afro-Caribbean and/or refugees/asylees.

Study goals include:

- Offering practical, actionable information for improving population health & health equity in New Jersey.
- A Focus on trauma, stress, resilience, and population health and wellbeing outcomes.
- Generalizing to the NJ population with specific focus on multigenerational families, immigrant groups, racial/ethnic minorities & low-income communities.
- Engaging in a strong state-level and community advisory process.
- Providing multi-modal communication and engagement with NJ communities & policy audiences, and
- Execute a robust, multi-pronged sustainability plan.

In this manuscript, attention is given to the study's multi-stage probability sample design, the use of address-based sampling (ABS) and the model-based oversampling strategies utilized to help to increase the yields and precision of survey estimates of recent immigrant populations in the state and of multigenerational households. To help ensure target survey response rates and sample targets are achieved, the sample design is further segmented into three distinct and representative subsamples, surveyed over three distinct data collection operational periods to help best utilize the available field staff in an efficient and effective manner and permitting fast-track study estimates prior to the conclusion of the survey. The estimation and weighting strategies implemented to correct for disproportional sampling, survey nonresponse and poststratification will also be summarized. In addition, planned study investigations are presented that examine ways in which the stress and resilience experiences of the study participants, including factors related to the COVID-19 pandemic, impact their health and well-being.

2. Overview of the Sample Design

The New Jersey Population Health Cohort Study has a goal of state-wide representative estimates with an emphasis on 1) oversampling recent immigrants and 2) oversampling multigenerational households. Additionally, there is a goal of ensuring adequate sample sizes for racial/ethnic minority and low-income groups. The goals of this study are achieved through a multi-stage probability sampling design.

The probability-based sampling design explicitly oversamples recent immigrants and multigenerational households at distinct stages, and is expected to oversample Hispanic and Black populations as shown in Table 1. In addition, the design is expected to represent the Asian population and households in the lower income quintile (household income less than or equal to \$27,800) in alignment with their proportional representation in New Jersey.

Table 1. Comparison of Population and Estimated Sample Percentages for Select Domains

Domain	Population Percentage*	Estimated Sample Percentage
Recent Immigrants	4.5	5.1
Hispanic	20.4	22.8
Black	12.7	14.4
Asian	9.5	9.7
Low Income Household	20.0	20.2

*Source: 2015-2019 5-year American Community Survey.

A total of 96,552 housing units will be selected for the study. Assuming a 5% response rate, approximately 4,800 responding households are anticipated for the probability-based sample, yielding 6,000 completed survey interviews at the individual level.

Overall, the sample design implements a four-stage probability sampling approach to select N=6,000 individuals living in New Jersey households. In addition to being designed to represent the State's households overall, the design oversamples multi-generational and low-income families and non-Hispanic Black and Hispanic individuals. We use a clustered, address-based sample (ABS) to enable efficient in-person data collection. Sampling is performed by RTI International using its augmented ABS sampling frame (Amaya et al., 2018).

Families (defined as a group of persons living in a household who are related by blood, marriage/cohabitation, adoption, or guardianship) are considered multi-generational if they have members in more than one of the age groups: teens (ages 14-17), young adult (18-39), middle adult (40-59) or older (60+). In such multi-generational families, we probabilistically select and recruit one member from each generation. The geographic sampling design is also intended to support sub-state regional representation, including urban and non-urban areas.

The four probability sampling stages are:

1. The selection of 30 primary sampling units (PSUs), drawn from 73 US Census Public Use Microdata Areas (PUMAs). Seven diverse PSUs of special public policy interest are selected with certainty and the others are selected probabilistically, oversampling areas with high shares of immigrants.
2. The selection of 23 Secondary Sampling Units (SSUs) per PSU, drawn from Census Block Groups. High-immigrant SSUs are oversampled.
3. The initial selection of 200 Housing Units (HUs) in each SSU. Using models developed by RTI, addresses likely to have multi-generational families are oversampled (RTI, 2022). Additional subsampling of the HUs in each SSU is then undertaken, resulting in 96,552 HUs subsampled to achieve the completion of the necessary number of household interviews to yield 6000 completed interviews at the individual level.
4. Within selected HU, probabilistically select families (if more than one is present) and family members aged 14 and older to be invited for participation. To implement stage 4 of the sampling strategy, we ask a knowledgeable resident of each sampled household to complete a web-based or telephone enumeration questionnaire. This brief survey records the number and demographic characteristics of each household resident from which one family (multi-family households) and family members are selected to recruit for study participation.

Stage 1 Sampling: Primary Sampling Units (PSUs) – (PUMAs)

Public use microdata areas (PUMAs) are sub-state geographic units created by the Census Bureau. They are large enough to have microdata from the American Community Survey (ACS) published for each area and each have at least 100,000 people. New Jersey has 73 PUMAs in the state. The primary sampling units (PSUs) for this survey are constructed from these PUMAs. Most PSUs consist of only 1 PUMA with an exception being for Jersey City and Newark City, which are each comprised of 2 PUMAs.

The PUMAs are sampled proportional to size where the size is defined as:

$$MOS_i = PopNonImm_i + 3 \times PopImm_i$$

where $PopNonImm_i$ is the population which are not recent immigrants in PSU i and $PopImm_i$ is the population which are recent immigrants in PSU i where recent immigrants are defined as the population entering the US since 2010 according to the 2015-2019 ACS¹. This specification oversamples areas with more recent immigrants. As noted, 30 primary sampling units (PSUs) are selected from 73 US Census Public Use Microdata Areas (PUMAs) to represent the state.

3. Scheduling PSU releases

The original design specified that interviewing would occur in 3 distinct waves with sample included in a representative subset of the PSUs each wave. The waves are characterized by an unequal number of PSUs released for each of the data collection operational periods to help best utilize the available field staff in an efficient and effective manner. There are 8, 10, and 12 PSUs released in waves 1, 2, and 3, respectively. Samples are released via representative subsets of PSUs to take into account field staff capacity and travel requirements. Consequently, each wave serves as a representative sample of the targeted study population in New Jersey, though the variances of wave specific survey estimates will be substantially larger than those achieved for the full study sample. As each wave specific sample is added, the variance of the pooled estimates will be noticeable reduced. The attraction of the design to permit wave specific estimates of the target population in New Jersey is the acquisition of fast-track survey estimates. This model allows for survey results to be analyzed and published for earlier waves and not require the entire data collection to be completed prior to learning of the study findings.

4. Subsequent Stages of Sample Selection

Stage 2 Sampling: Second Stage Units (SSUs) - (CBGs)

Census block groups (CBGs) are the smallest area that Census publishes 5-year ACS estimates. In New Jersey, there are 6,320 CBGs with an average of 572 housing units and median of 506.5 housing units ranging from 0 to 4,347 housing units. Using an internally developed algorithm, secondary sampling units (SSUs) are constructed from CBGs by collapsing neighboring CBGs within each PUMA as necessary until all SSUs have at least 300 housing units as 200 housing units are later sampled within each SSU. After constructing the SSUs, a random sample of 23 SSUs is selected from each PSU. These are selected proportional to size where the size is defined as:

$$MOS_{i,j} = PopNonImm_{i,j} + 3 \times PopImm_{i,j}$$

where $PopNonImm_{i,j}$ is the population who are not recent immigrants in SSU j in PSU i and $PopImm_{i,j}$ is the population who are recent immigrants in SSU j in PSU i . In total, 690 SSUs are sampled.

Stage 3 Sampling: Housing Units

¹ All ACS data in this report is obtained from the 2015-2019 5-year American Community Survey. As of 1/18/2022, the 2020 ACS data is yet to be released.

Within each SSU, the housing unit frame was constructed using addresses from an address-based sampling (ABS) frame derived from the U.S. Postal Service's Computerized Delivery Sequence file. Addresses on the ABS frame are assigned to SSUs through a process called geocoding. Geocoding involves assigning a location (latitude and longitude) to an address by comparing the descriptive location elements in the address to those present in geocoding locator files. Addresses are geocoded using ESRI's Business Analyst USA Composite locator which is comprised of several individual locators. The input addresses are first matched against the locator with the highest geographic accuracy which is the rooftop location of addresses. If a suitable match is not found, those unmatched input addresses cascade to the next locator, which interpolates the position along a street using the address range. This process continues through the locators, with each one returning decreasing geographic accuracy. If no match can be found for the last locator, the input address is returned as unmatched.

Within each SSU, a sample size of 200 housing units was originally planned to be selected. Using survey data and address data from a prior study, a model was built to predict whether households are multigenerational. The survey used in modeling was a nationally representative sample which included questions on the ages of the residents of the household. Using these ages, a multigenerational indicator was derived and used as the outcome in the model. Data used in the model as covariates came from a proprietary marketing database which has data on most addresses in the United States and area level data from the ACS. Addresses are oversampled in the high-density stratum with a higher predicted probability of multigenerational households in the SSU.

Drop points are mail receptacles shared by multiple housing units (drop units). Drop points with more than 3 drop units were excluded prior to sampling but make up an exceedingly small portion of addresses in New Jersey. If a drop point was selected, all drop units at that drop point are selected. Including drop units, the sample for Wave 1 has 38,694 cases. Wave 2 and Wave 3 will be selected at a later date as the household oversampling rate may change.

Stage 4 Sampling: Within Household Selection

A roster of each household will be collected and the relationships between all people age 14 and over will be obtained. A family will be randomly selected from the household where families with more generations are more likely to be selected. Then within the sampled family, 1 person from each generation present will be selected at random.

Generations are defined by the following age ranges:

- Teen: 14-17
- Young adult: 18-39
- Middle-aged adult: 40-59
- Older adult: 60+

Within each household, the following oversampling factors will be used to select a family:

Number of generations	Family size: Number of people age 14+ in family				
	1	2	3	4	5+
1	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4
2	-	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8
3	-	-	1.9	2.0	2.1
4	-	-	-	2.2	2.3

After a family is randomly selected, 1 person from each generation of that family is randomly selected with equal probability within that generation. Examples for selection of families and individuals is included in the following Table.

Household 1

This has 3 unrelated roommates:

Family	Person	Generation
1	1	18-39
2	1	18-39
3	1	18-39

This then will lead to the following probabilities:

Family	Number generations	Family size	Weight	Probability
1	1	1	1.0	1/3
2	1	1	1.0	1/3
3	1	1	1.0	1/3
Total			3	1

Assume Family 1 was selected. It only has 1 person so that person will be selected.

Household 2

This household has a couple with two children along with a roommate and the roommate's girlfriend. The roommate and girlfriend are assumed to NOT be treated as a family.

Family	Person	Generation
1	1	18-39
1	2	18-39
1	3	14-17
1	4	0-13
2	1	18-39
3	1	18-39

Family	Number generations	Family size	Weight	Probability
1	2	3	1.6	$1.6/3.6=0.444$
2	1	1	1.0	$1.0/3.6=0.278$
3	1	1	1.0	$1.0/3.6=0.278$

Total	3.6	
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Assume Family 1 was selected. Then Person 3 will be selected and Person 1 or 2 will be randomly selected with equal probability. Person 4 is not eligible.

Household 3

This household has a young adult couple, a brother to one person in the young adult couple, the brother's girlfriend, and the parents of the siblings. This is only 2 families.

Family	Person	Generation
1	1 (couple)	18-39
1	2 (couple)	18-39
1	3 (brother)	18-39
1	4 (parent 1)	60+
1	5 (parent 2)	60+
2	1 (brother's girlfriend)	18-39

Family	Number generations	Family size	Weight	Probability
1	2	5	1.8	$1.8/2.8=0.643$
2	1	1	1.0	$1.0/2.8=0.357$
Total			2.8	

Assume Family 1 was selected. Then person 1, 2 or 3 will be randomly selected with equal probability (1/3) and Person 4 or 5 will be selected with equal probability (1/2).

5. Summary

In summary, the New Jersey Population Health Cohort (NJHealth) Study was designed to improve the understanding and generate knowledge about factors that affect population health and opportunities to advance equity promoting policies in the state. The study will collect biometrics, survey responses and other granular data over time on major outcomes such as stress, resilience, trauma and cognitive function from a broad cross-section of the population across multiple generations, with additional targeting of low-income residents and diverse immigrant group.

Study outcome domains include psychosocial components and measures of physical health and health care utilization. Assessments of stress, anxiety, loneliness, depressive symptoms, religiosity and well-being are to be studied. Additional physical attributes under study include metabolic, clinical, sleep, cognition, physical performance and function, BMI, and medical comorbidities. Attention is also given to the use of essential health care services, and access/barriers encountered. Study research topics under consideration include: How do specific life events impact health and well-being?; What factors contribute to resiliency and positive health outcomes, despite or due to stressful experiences?; How do intergenerational family dynamics impact these relationships?; What roles do immigrant experiences play in exposure to stress, resilience, and population health outcomes?; What roles do race and ethnicity play in population health and health equity?; and What have been some of the most significant impacts of COVID-19?

The initial sample design objective was to select a representative sample of approximately 10,000 participants from broad sections of the population in the state. Adjustments to these sample targets were recently made to support the inclusion of a respondent-driven sample (RDS) arm. More specifically, the study also includes some nonprobability-based design features to enhance the participation of rare population subgroups that include recent immigrants. Revised sample size targets resulted in a design that is expected to yield approximately 4,800 responding households and 6,000 completed survey interviews obtained from the probability-based sample selection process. The remaining respondents 4,000 are to be obtained from the respondent-driven sample (RDS) arm. Individuals sampled via these non-random selection schemes will limit their generalizability but have the potential to support behavioral analyses.

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References

- Amaya A, Zimmer S, Morton K, Harter R. (2018). Does undercoverage on the U.S. Address-based sampling frame translate to coverage bias? *Sociolo Methods Res.* 2018;50:812-836. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0049124118782539>
- American Association for Public Opinion Research (2016). Address-based sampling. Report prepared for AAPOR Council by the Task Force on Address-based Sampling; R. Harter, Chair. Oakbrook Terrace, IL: AAPOR. [https://www.aapor.org/getattachment/Education-Resources/Reports/AAPOR_Report_1_7_16_CLEAN-COPY-FINAL-\(2\).pdf](https://www.aapor.org/getattachment/Education-Resources/Reports/AAPOR_Report_1_7_16_CLEAN-COPY-FINAL-(2).pdf)
- American Association for Public Opinion Research (2018). Spam Flagging and Call Blocking and Its Impact on Survey Research; D. Dutwin, Chair. Oakbrook Terrace, IL: AAPOR. https://www.aapor.org/AAPOR_Main/media/MainSiteFiles/AAPOR-Spam-Report-021218.pdf
- Biemer, P. P., Murphy, J. J., Zimmer, S. A., Berry, J., Lewis, K., & Deng, S. (2016, May). *A test of web/PAPI protocols and incentives for the Residential Energy Consumption Survey*. Presented at Annual meeting of the American Association for Public Opinion Research, Austin, TX.
- Fellows, I. E. (2012), "Exponential Family Random Network Models," unpublished Ph.D. dissertation, University of California, Los Angeles, Dept. of Statistics.
- Folsom R. E., & Singh, A. C. (2000). The generalized exponential model for sampling weight calibration for extreme values, nonresponse, and poststratification. In *Proceedings of the 2000 Joint Statistical Meetings, American Statistical Association, Survey Research Methods Section, Indianapolis, IN* (pp. 598–603). Alexandria, VA: American Statistical Association.

- Gile, K.J., Beaudry, I.S., Handcock, M.S., & Ott, M.Q. (2018). Methods for Inference from Respondent-Driven Sampling Data. *Annual Review of Statistics and its Application*, 5, 65-93.
- Handcock, M.S (2017). Discussion of “Adaptive and network sampling for inference and interventions in changing populations” by Steve K. Thompson. *Journal of Survey Statistics and Methodology*, 5, 29–33.
- Harter, R., & McMichael, J. P. (2012). Scope and coverage of landline and cell phone numbers appended to address frames. In *Joint Statistical Meetings Proceedings, Survey Research Methods Section* (pp. 3651–3665). Alexandria, VA: American Statistical Association.
- Harter, R., McMichael, J., Brown, D., Amaya, A. E., Buskirk, T., & Malarek, D. (2018). Telephone appends for address-based samples—An introduction. (RTI Press Publication No. OP-0050- 1802). Research Triangle Park, NC: RTI Press. <https://www.rti.org/rti-press-publication/telephone-append-address-based-samples%E2%80%94introduction>
- Heckathorn, D. D. (1997), “Respondent-Driven Sampling: A New Approach to the Study of Hidden Populations,” *Social Problems*, 44, 174–199.
- Kish, Leslie. 1965. *Survey Sampling*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- McMichael, J. P., & Wiant, K. F. (2019). Improvements in sample design with address-level prediction models. *American Association for Public Opinion Research Annual Conference*, Toronto, Canada.
- Salganik, M. J., and D. D. Heckathorn (2004). “Sampling and Estimation in Hidden Populations Using Respondent-Driven Sampling,” *Sociological Methodology*, 34, 193–239.
- Shook-Sa, B. E., Currivan, D. B., McMichael, J. P., & Iannacchione, V. G. (2013). Extending the coverage of address-based sampling frames: beyond the USPS Computerized Delivery Sequence File. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 77, 994-1005.
- Volz, E., and D. D. Heckathorn (2008), “Probability Based Estimation Theory for Respondent Driven Sampling,” *Journal of Official Statistics*, 24, 79–97.
- Wiant, K. F., & McMichael, J. P. (2019). Evaluating strategies for identifying rare populations within an address-based sample. Paper presented at *American Association for Public Opinion Research Annual Conference*, Toronto, Canada.
- Zimmer, S., Morton, K and Cohen, S.B. (2022). *New Jersey Population Health Cohort Study Sampling Design Plan*. Project Report submitted to the Institute for Health, Health Care Policy, and Aging Research Rutgers University.